

ISic2760

I.Sicily inscription 2760

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

prayer

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Dianae Fons

Place of origin (modern)

Comiso

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR112490

1. [Ἐνόν]νό[ματ][ιK](υρίο) [υπρὸς]ἀ[μπελ]□ [ναν] (ἀμπελῶνα) ΟΤΡΙΑΑΡΕ
Ἀβιμήλ, [λασφ]φ[έν], [Ἀμι]μήλ, [Ἐλο]έλ, ' [Ε]

2. [άο] [Ἀζα]ήρ, [Κορφ]φλιή[λ], Φαχθοβάρ, ΑΧ Ἄδοῦ[ά]ήλ Ε Ϙ
[ΕΧΕΡΜΑΡΘ]ἈβράξΙΑΦΕΝ]

3. [---ΑΧΑΕΛ]Ἰ[ΜΕ] [ΡΜΟΡ]Μ[Ο]ΡΚΑΘΑΛΟΚ [ΘΑ] ΟΔ [Α]Μ[Ε] [ΛΜΟΥΚΗΠΡΟΣ]Ἰ[Η]
[ΝΟΣ]

4. [---Ἐρα]ήλ[λ] [ἀμ]ήν, Β Ἐρ[ά]ήλ ΘΥΛΑΤΑ, Α, ΣΕ [ΤΗΤΟ] [ΦΙ](ησο) [ϚΧρ](ιστ)[έ],
[όπλοι]

5. [θύνας πληθ]ύνας --- [ίς εἰς] [τίν] τήν [θαλάσσην], πλοῖθυνον πλήθυνον
καὶ [τὸν] ἄ [μπελον] [ίς] εἰς [τὸν ἀμπελ]□ [να] [ν] ἀμπελῶνα

6. [ΟΛΜΕΤΡ]

7.

8.

Edition: PHI316301

1. [έν] ὀνόματι Κ (ρίο) υ πρὸς ἀμπελῶν[αν] ΟΤΡΙΑΑΡΕ Ἀβιμήλ, Λασφέν, Ἀμιήλ,
Ἐλοέλ, Ἐ-

2. άο, Ἀζαήρ, Κορφλιήλ, Φαχθοβάρ, [— — —]ΑΧ, Ἄδοναήλ, ΕϘΕΧΕΡΜΑΡΘ

Ἀβράξ ΙΑΦΕΝ

3. [— — —]ΑΧΑΕΛΜΕΡΜΟΡΜΟΡΚΑΘΑΛΟΚ ΘΑ[— — —]ΟΔ
ΑΜΕΛΜΟΥΚΗΠΡΟΣΑΗΝΟC

4. [— — —] Ἐραήλ, ἀμήν, Β Ἐραήλ ΘΥΛΑΤΑ,Α,ÇΕ[— — —]ΤΗΤΟ Φ Ἴ(ησο) Ὑ Χρ
(ιστ) ἐ , ὁ πλοι-

5. [θύνας — — — ἰς] τὴν θαλάσση[ν], πλοῖθνον καὶ τὸν ἄμπ[ελον] ἰς τ[ὸν
ἄμπε]λῶν[α]ν

6. ΟΛΜΕΤΡ

7. ²signa magica² ²duae palmae² ²signa magica²

8. ²signa magica² □ □ □ □ α□ω □ □ □

9.

Edition: PHI329961

1. [ἐ] ν ὄν ὄ,μ,α,τ [ι Κ(υρίο)υ πρὸς] ἄ,μ,π,ελο[ν] #⁷ΤΟΙΑΑΡΕΑΒΙ#⁷ [— — —]

2. [— — —] ΦΑΧΘΟΒΑΡΚ.ΧΑΔΟΡΑΙΛΕ [— — — — — — — — —]

3. [— — —]Ι.ΟΡ#⁷ΑΘΑΛ Ο Α. #⁷ΟΔ [— — — — — — — — —]

4. [— — —] ΟΡΑΙΛΘΥΝC. . . Ε [— — — — — — — — —]

5. [— — —] Η. ΤΛΟΙΘΥΝΟΝ#⁷ΑΝ,Ο. ΑΙ [— — — — — — — — —]

6. ²rhombus² ²palmae²

7. ²rhombus² □ □ □ □ □

8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284749

EDR 112490

EDCS 64600457

PHI 316301

PHI 329961

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2760. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387357>